

Article

A Unified Constant-Time Switch Rule for Constructing Edge-Disjoint Hamiltonian Cycles in Gaussian Networks

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Abstract

Gaussian networks are degree-four symmetric interconnection networks defined over residue classes of Gaussian integers. Earlier work showed that, when the generator $\alpha = a + bi$ satisfies $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, the real and imaginary dimensions directly form two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles. A later construction extended the result to the non-coprime case $\gcd(a, b) = d > 1$, but its proof relied on long node-sequence tables and separate odd/even cases for d . This paper presents a unified closed-form construction that covers both $d = 1$ and $d > 1$, and both odd and even d , without separate case tables. In the rectangular representation with d rows and $r = (a^2 + b^2)/d$ columns, the construction uses a constant-time local switch rule, meaning constant time per individual switch, for each $q = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1$ at column $a_q = q - 1$. Each switch removes two horizontal edges and inserts two vertical edges. The switched horizontal structure forms the first Hamiltonian cycle, while its edge-complement in the Gaussian network forms the second Hamiltonian cycle. Thus, the full edge set is partitioned into two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles. The construction requires $O(d)$ switch-generation time and $O(N)$ time to list the two cycles, where $N = a^2 + b^2$. Exhaustive validation for all $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$, excluding only the degenerate $N = 2$ network, and large-scale validation up to $N = 3,250,000$ confirm implementation correctness and demonstrate practical scalability.

Keywords: edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles; Gaussian networks; Gaussian integers; interconnection networks; Hamiltonian cycle; parallel processing; successor rule; algebraic networks

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1. Introduction

Gaussian networks are algebraic interconnection networks defined over quotient rings of Gaussian integers. They are regular degree-four networks whose vertices are residue classes modulo a Gaussian integer $\alpha = a + bi$, and whose links correspond to adding or subtracting the Gaussian units 1 and i [1,2]. Because they are algebraically regular and symmetric, Gaussian networks are useful for modeling toroidal-like interconnection networks with compact routing and wrap-around structure.

Hamiltonian cycles are important in interconnection networks because a Hamiltonian cycle embeds a spanning ring through all processors. Such rings are useful for broadcasting, all-to-all communication, and load-balanced message circulation. Multiple edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles (EDHCs) are even more useful because they provide independent spanning rings, allowing communication traffic to be distributed and improving tolerance

to edge faults [3–8]. Recent work continues to use EDHCs as a structural tool for fault-tolerant broadcasting and data-center/interconnection-network design [7–9].

For Gaussian networks, the EDHC problem naturally splits according to

$$d = \gcd(a, b). \quad (1)$$

When $d = 1$, the real dimension alone forms a Hamiltonian cycle and the imaginary dimension alone forms another Hamiltonian cycle. This gives two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles immediately [2]. When $d > 1$, however, the real-dimension edges decompose into d disjoint cycles, and the imaginary-dimension edges also decompose into d disjoint cycles. The non-coprime case therefore requires a splicing mechanism to join these smaller cycles. The non-coprime case was previously solved by Albader and Bose using explicit node-sequence tables for odd and even d [10]. The present paper is self-contained: all definitions, switch rules, correctness proofs, and algorithms needed for the unified construction are included here.

Compared with the previous non-coprime construction [10], the main advantage of the proposed rule is threefold. First, in terms of complexity of description, the earlier construction required separate parity-dependent sequences, whereas the present method uses the single formula $a_q = q - 1$. Second, in terms of readability, the proof is organized around two transparent splice trees rather than long tables of vertices. Third, in terms of implementation, the switch set can be generated by one short loop over $q = 1, \dots, d - 1$, which makes the construction easier to verify, reproduce, and adapt in software.

This paper presents a unified and more concise solution. It shows that one closed-form switching rule handles all cases:

$$q = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1, \quad a_q = q - 1. \quad (2)$$

For $d = 1$, there are no switches and the construction reduces exactly to the classical coprime case. For $d > 1$, the same formula splices the d horizontal cycles into one Hamiltonian cycle and simultaneously splices the complementary vertical cycles into the second Hamiltonian cycle. Thus, the new construction unifies the earlier $d = 1$ result and the later $d > 1$ result in one algorithmic framework. The unification occurs at three levels: it covers both the trivial coprime case $d = 1$ and the non-trivial non-coprime case $d > 1$; it eliminates the need to distinguish odd and even values of d ; and it replaces the previous parity-dependent lookup tables by the deterministic formula $a_q = q - 1$. The phrase “constant-time switch rule” refers to the fact that each individual switch is generated by a constant number of arithmetic operations; explicitly listing the resulting Hamiltonian cycles still requires $O(N)$ time because each cycle contains N vertices. From a graph-theoretic perspective, the result gives an explicit decomposition of the full edge set of every nondegenerate Gaussian network into two Hamiltonian 2-factors.

The main contributions are:

- a unified EDHC construction for nondegenerate Gaussian networks that covers $d = 1$, $d > 1$, odd d , and even d ;
- a closed-form constant-time-per-switch rule $a_q = q - 1$ that replaces the previous odd/even case tables;
- complete algorithms for constructing the switch set and traversing the two Hamiltonian cycles;
- a proof that the switched graph is a Hamiltonian cycle, that its edge-complement is also a Hamiltonian cycle, and that the two cycles are edge-disjoint;
- exhaustive validation for all $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$ and large-scale validation up to 3,250,000 vertices.

2. Related Work and Positioning

Gaussian networks were introduced and studied as algebraic models of toroidal networks in [1]. The topology of Gaussian and Eisenstein–Jacobi interconnection networks was further developed in [2], including distance, routing, and Hamiltonian-cycle properties. In particular, when $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, the two natural dimensions of G_{a+bi} give two EDHCs.

The non-coprime Gaussian case was later addressed by Albader and Bose [10]. In that case, the $+1$ edges form $d = \gcd(a, b)$ disjoint cycles and the $+i$ edges form another d disjoint cycles.

The present paper differs from both earlier works. Unlike [2], it is not restricted to $d = 1$, and unlike [10], it is not restricted to $d > 1$. Instead, it gives a single algorithm that covers both. Table 1 summarizes the difference.

Table 1. Positioning of the present construction.

Work	Case Covered	Construction Style
Flahive and Bose [2]	$d = 1$	Direct dimension cycles
Albader and Bose [10]	$d > 1$	Odd/even sequence tables
This paper	$d = 1$ and $d > 1$	Unified closed-form switch rule

Outside Gaussian networks, EDHCs have been studied in several interconnection topologies, including hypercubes and k -ary n -cubes [3], butterfly graphs [4], twisted and locally twisted cubes [5,11], augmented cubes [6], folded locally twisted cubes and folded crossed cubes [7], balanced hypercubes [12], and BCube data-center networks [8]. Recent graph-theoretic work has also studied EDHCs in symmetric and Cayley-type graphs and spanning disjoint cycles in hypercube-like networks [9,13]. These works show that EDHC constructions remain active and relevant for both network theory and communication applications.

These studies share a common objective with the present paper: they seek multiple spanning cycles that can support communication, load distribution, or fault tolerance. Their structural tools, however, are different. Hypercube-like networks typically use recursive or product-graph structure, while BCube-type networks use data-center layering. Gaussian networks are Cayley graphs over quotient rings of Gaussian integers, so the present construction uses quotient arithmetic, rectangular coordinates, and edge-complement switching. This distinction explains why the EDHC problem is usually treated separately for different interconnection-network families and why a closed-form rule for Gaussian networks is useful in its own right. The present paper does not attempt a complexity classification for all hypercube variants; instead, it exploits the algebraic structure that is specific to Gaussian networks.

3. Preliminaries

Let

$$\mathbb{Z}[i] = \{x + yi : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}\} \tag{3}$$

be the ring of Gaussian integers. The norm of $\alpha = a + bi$ is

$$N(\alpha) = a^2 + b^2. \tag{4}$$

We use the following standard graph-theoretic terminology, as commonly used in interconnection-network studies [3,14,15]. A graph is k -regular if every vertex has degree k . A spanning subgraph of a graph G is a subgraph that contains all vertices of G . A Hamiltonian cycle is a cycle that visits every vertex exactly once and returns to its starting vertex. Two Hamiltonian cycles are edge-disjoint if they do not share any edge; an edge-disjoint

Hamiltonian-cycle (EDHC) construction therefore provides multiple spanning cycles whose edge sets are mutually disjoint.

Definition 1 (Gaussian network). *Let $\alpha = a + bi \neq 0$. The Gaussian network generated by α is the graph*

$$G_\alpha = (V, E), \tag{5}$$

where

$$V = \mathbb{Z}[i]/(\alpha), \tag{6}$$

and two vertices $\beta, \gamma \in V$ are adjacent if and only if

$$\beta - \gamma \equiv \pm 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \pm i \pmod{\alpha}. \tag{7}$$

The number of vertices is

$$|V| = N = a^2 + b^2. \tag{8}$$

Throughout the paper, assume $0 < a \leq b$. Let

$$d = \gcd(a, b), \quad r = \frac{a^2 + b^2}{d}. \tag{9}$$

As a preview of the worked example in Section 7, for $\alpha = 4 + 4i$, we obtain $N = 32$, $d = 4$, and $r = 8$. Hence, the rectangle representation contains four rows and eight columns. The complete construction for this example is shown later in Section 7.2.

Rectangle Representation

The rectangle representation uses the complete residue system

$$S = \{(x, y) : 0 \leq x < r, 0 \leq y < d\}. \tag{10}$$

Thus, each vertex is represented by a pair (x, y) , with x taken modulo r and y restricted to $0, \dots, d - 1$.

Let $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfy

$$ua + vb = d. \tag{11}$$

Define

$$n \equiv av - bu \pmod{r}. \tag{12}$$

Then, the rectangle representation has the wrap relation

$$-i \equiv n + (d - 1)i \pmod{\alpha}. \tag{13}$$

Consequently,

$$di \equiv -n \pmod{\alpha}. \tag{14}$$

The moves in rectangle coordinates are:

$$E(x, y) = (x + 1 \pmod{r}, y), \tag{15}$$

$$W(x, y) = (x - 1 \pmod{r}, y), \tag{16}$$

$$N_i(x, y) = \begin{cases} (x, y + 1), & 0 \leq y < d - 1, \\ (x - n \bmod r, 0), & y = d - 1, \end{cases} \tag{17}$$

$$S_i(x, y) = \begin{cases} (x, y - 1), & 0 < y \leq d - 1, \\ (x + n \bmod r, d - 1), & y = 0. \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

Here, E, W, N_i, S_i denote east, west, north, and south moves.

Remark 1. Note that the x -coordinate changes by $-n$ only when the $+i$ move wraps from row $d - 1$ to row 0 ; n is not subtracted at every vertical step.

Proposition 1. The wrap shift n is divisible by d .

Proof. Write $a = da_1$ and $b = db_1$. Then,

$$n \equiv av - bu = d(a_1v - b_1u) \pmod{r}. \tag{19}$$

Also,

$$r = \frac{a^2 + b^2}{d} = d(a_1^2 + b_1^2), \tag{20}$$

so r is divisible by d . Hence, the chosen residue n modulo r is a multiple of d . \square

4. The Unified Switching Construction

Starting from all horizontal edges, which form d disjoint row cycles each of length r , the construction performs $d - 1$ local switches.

For $d = 1$, the switch set is empty. The horizontal cycle and vertical cycle are already Hamiltonian, so the construction reduces to the known coprime case.

For $d > 1$, define for every

$$q = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1 \tag{21}$$

the switching column

$$a_q = q - 1. \tag{22}$$

Define the four switch vertices

$$A_q = (a_q, q) = (q - 1, q), \tag{23}$$

$$B_q = (a_q + 1, q) = (q, q), \tag{24}$$

$$C_q = A_q + i, \tag{25}$$

$$D_q = B_q + i. \tag{26}$$

The switch removes the two horizontal edges

$$A_q B_q, \quad C_q D_q, \tag{27}$$

and inserts the two vertical edges

$$A_q C_q, \quad B_q D_q. \tag{28}$$

Let R be the set of removed horizontal edges and S the set of inserted vertical edges:

$$R = \{A_q B_q, C_q D_q : 1 \leq q \leq d - 1\}, \tag{29}$$

$$S = \{A_q C_q, B_q D_q : 1 \leq q \leq d - 1\}. \tag{30}$$

Let E_h be the set of all horizontal edges and E_v the set of all vertical edges. Define

$$E(H_1) = (E_h \setminus R) \cup S, \tag{31}$$

and

$$E(H_2) = (E_v \setminus S) \cup R. \tag{32}$$

Equivalently, H_2 is the edge-complement of H_1 inside G_α , using precisely the graph edges not selected by H_1 . Intuitively, G_α is 4-regular and H_1 uses exactly two incident edges at every vertex; the remaining two incident edges at each vertex form the complementary 2-regular graph H_2 .

Figure 1 illustrates the local switch operation. The dashed horizontal edges are removed from H_1 and become part of H_2 , while the solid vertical switch edges are inserted into H_1 and removed from H_2 .

Figure 1. Local switch s_q . Blue denotes horizontal edges removed from H_1 (shown dashed in the diagram), whereas red denotes vertical switch edges inserted into H_1 (shown solid). The two dashed horizontal edges A_qB_q and C_qD_q are removed from the horizontal construction of H_1 and are assigned to H_2 . The two solid vertical edges A_qC_q and B_qD_q are inserted into H_1 and excluded from H_2 .

The global effect of the same switch family is summarized in Figure 2. Panel (a) shows the row-cycle splice tree used to form H_1 : the switches connect the horizontal row cycles through $C_0 - C_{d-1} - C_{d-2} - \dots - C_1$. Panel (b) shows the complementary splice tree used to form H_2 : the vertical residue-class cycles $V_j = \{(x, y) : x \equiv j \pmod{d}\}$ are connected through $V_0 - V_1 - \dots - V_{d-1}$. Thus, the same local switch family has two complementary global effects.

Figure 2. Conceptual effect of the unified switch rule. **(a)** The row cycles C_0, \dots, C_{d-1} are spliced into one Hamiltonian cycle H_1 . The switches s_1, \dots, s_{d-1} create the splice tree $C_0 - C_{d-1} - C_{d-2} - \dots - C_1$. **(b)** The vertical residue-class cycles V_0, \dots, V_{d-1} , where $V_j = \{(x, y) : x \equiv j \pmod{d}\}$, are spliced by complementary switch edges into one Hamiltonian cycle H_2 through the tree $V_0 - V_1 - \dots - V_{d-1}$. The arrows indicate the construction flow from disjoint cycles to a splice tree and then to one Hamiltonian cycle. Blue denotes the horizontal/ H_1 construction, red denotes the vertical/ H_2 construction, and black arrows denote the construction flow. The ellipses denote omitted intermediate cycles or indices.

5. Correctness Proof

We first state a basic cycle-splicing fact.

Remark 2 (Two-edge splicing principle). *Let C_1 and C_2 be two vertex-disjoint cycles. If one edge is removed from each cycle and two valid cross edges are inserted so that the resulting graph remains 2-regular, then the operation splices C_1 and C_2 into one cycle containing all vertices of $C_1 \cup C_2$. This is the local cycle-splicing principle used in the construction below.*

Lemma 1. *For $1 \leq q \leq d - 1$, each local switch is valid, and no two switches use the same removed or inserted edge.*

Proof. By construction, A_q and B_q differ by $+1$, so $A_q B_q$ is horizontal. Also, $C_q = A_q + i$ and $D_q = B_q + i$. Therefore, C_q and D_q differ by $+1$, so $C_q D_q$ is horizontal. The edges $A_q C_q$ and $B_q D_q$ are vertical by definition.

The removed edge A_qB_q lies on row q , while C_qD_q lies on row $q + 1 \pmod d$. The formula $a_q = q - 1$ gives distinct switch positions across the row adjacencies. The inserted vertical edges have lower endpoints A_q and B_q , which are distinct for different q . Hence, the inserted edges are distinct. The only row that appears in two consecutive switches is handled at different horizontal columns, so the removed horizontal edges are also distinct. \square

Lemma 2. For $d > 1$, the graph H_1 is a Hamiltonian cycle.

Proof. Before switching, E_n consists of d disjoint row cycles:

$$C_0, C_1, \dots, C_{d-1}, \tag{33}$$

where C_y denotes the horizontal cycle in row y .

The switch at row q removes one horizontal edge from row q and one horizontal edge from row $q + 1$ for $1 \leq q \leq d - 2$. It then inserts two vertical edges between these two rows. Therefore, for $1 \leq q \leq d - 2$, switch s_q splices C_q with C_{q+1} . For the last switch, $q = d - 1$, the vertices $C_{d-1} = A_{d-1} + i$ and $D_{d-1} = B_{d-1} + i$ are obtained through the vertical wrap from row $d - 1$ to row 0 ; hence s_{d-1} splices C_{d-1} with C_0 .

Thus, the row-cycle adjacencies created by the switches are

switch	row cycles spliced
s_1	$C_1 \leftrightarrow C_2$
s_2	$C_2 \leftrightarrow C_3$
\vdots	\vdots
s_{d-2}	$C_{d-2} \leftrightarrow C_{d-1}$
s_{d-1}	$C_{d-1} \leftrightarrow C_0$.

(34)

These $d - 1$ adjacencies form a connected tree on the d row cycles. Equivalently, the row cycles are connected in the order

$$C_0 - C_{d-1} - C_{d-2} - \dots - C_2 - C_1. \tag{35}$$

By Remark 2, each switch reduces the number of cycles by one. Starting from d cycles and applying $d - 1$ switches leaves exactly one cycle. Since the switches preserve degree two and keep all vertices, the resulting cycle contains all N vertices. Therefore, H_1 is Hamiltonian. \square

Lemma 3. The vertical cycles before switching are indexed by $x \pmod d$.

Proof. A non-wrap vertical step changes (x, y) to $(x, y + 1)$ and therefore preserves $x \pmod d$. A wrap vertical step changes $(x, d - 1)$ to $(x - n, 0)$. By Proposition 1, n is divisible by d , so $x - n \equiv x \pmod d$. Hence, every vertical step preserves $x \pmod d$, and each vertical component is contained in one residue class modulo d .

It remains to show that each residue class forms a single cycle. Write

$$a = da_1, \quad b = db_1, \quad n = dn', \quad r = dr', \tag{36}$$

where

$$n' = a_1v - b_1u, \quad r' = a_1^2 + b_1^2. \tag{37}$$

Since $ua + vb = d$, we have $ua_1 + vb_1 = 1$, and therefore $\gcd(a_1, b_1) = 1$. We claim that $\gcd(n', r') = 1$. If a prime p divided both $n' = a_1v - b_1u$ and $r' = a_1^2 + b_1^2$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_1 &= a_1(ua_1 + vb_1) = ua_1^2 + va_1b_1 \equiv -ub_1^2 + va_1b_1 \\
 &= b_1(a_1v - b_1u) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{38}$$

Similarly, $b_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, contradicting $\gcd(a_1, b_1) = 1$. Hence, $\gcd(n', r') = 1$.

Now fix a residue class $c \pmod{d}$ and write its columns as $x = c + kd$, where $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{r'}$. After one full vertical traversal through the d rows, the wrap changes x by $-n = -dn'$, which induces the translation

$$k \mapsto k - n' \pmod{r'} \tag{39}$$

on $\mathbb{Z}_{r'}$. Because $\gcd(n', r') = 1$, this translation is a single cycle on $\mathbb{Z}_{r'}$. Thus, repeated full vertical wraps visit all r' columns in the fixed residue class before returning to the starting column. Each visited column contributes all d rows, so the vertical component has $dr' = r$ vertices. Therefore, each residue class $x \pmod{d}$ is exactly one vertical cycle of length r , and there are precisely d such cycles. \square

Lemma 4. For $d > 1$, the graph H_2 is a Hamiltonian cycle.

Proof. Before switching, E_v consists of d vertical cycles. By Lemma 3, these cycles are indexed by $x \pmod{d}$.

Consider the switch for a fixed q , where $1 \leq q \leq d - 1$. The horizontal edge

$$A_q B_q = ((q - 1, q), (q, q)) \tag{40}$$

connects the vertical-cycle index $q - 1$ to the vertical-cycle index q . Since $C_q = A_q + i$ and $D_q = B_q + i$, adding i preserves the x -coordinate modulo d by Lemma 3. Hence, $C_q D_q$ also connects the vertical-cycle index $q - 1$ to the vertical-cycle index q .

In H_2 , the two vertical edges $A_q C_q$ and $B_q D_q$ are removed from the corresponding vertical cycles, while the two horizontal edges $A_q B_q$ and $C_q D_q$ are inserted. By Remark 2, this splices the two vertical cycles indexed by $q - 1$ and q .

As q ranges from 1 to $d - 1$, the complement switches join the vertical-cycle indices through

$$0 - 1 - 2 - \dots - (d - 1), \tag{41}$$

which is a tree on the d vertical cycles. Therefore, the $d - 1$ complement switches reduce the d vertical cycles to one cycle. Since the switches preserve degree two and all vertices remain present, H_2 is Hamiltonian. \square

Lemma 5. For every nondegenerate Gaussian network with $N > 2$, the constructed graphs H_1 and H_2 are edge-disjoint and their edge sets partition $E(G_\alpha)$.

Proof. Let E_h be the set of edges generated by ± 1 , and let E_v be the set of edges generated by $\pm i$. Since $N > 2$, no undirected edge can be both horizontal and vertical. Otherwise, one would have $\pm 1 \equiv \pm i \pmod{\alpha}$, so α would divide one of $1 + i$ or $1 - i$, whose norm is 2, contradicting $N(\alpha) = N > 2$. Hence,

$$E_h \cap E_v = \emptyset. \tag{42}$$

Also,

$$E(G_\alpha) = E_h \cup E_v. \tag{43}$$

The switch construction chooses $R \subseteq E_h$ and $S \subseteq E_v$ and defines

$$E(H_1) = (E_h \setminus R) \cup S, \tag{44}$$

while

$$E(H_2) = (E_v \setminus S) \cup R. \tag{45}$$

Thus, every horizontal edge is placed in exactly one of H_1 and H_2 : the edges in R go to H_2 , and the edges in $E_h \setminus R$ remain in H_1 . Similarly, every vertical edge is placed in exactly one of H_1 and H_2 : the edges in S go to H_1 , and the edges in $E_v \setminus S$ remain in H_2 . Therefore,

$$E(H_1) \cap E(H_2) = \emptyset \tag{46}$$

and

$$E(H_1) \cup E(H_2) = E(G_\alpha). \tag{47}$$

□

Theorem 1. Let $\alpha = a + bi$ with $0 < a \leq b$, let $N = a^2 + b^2 > 2$, and let G_α be the corresponding nondegenerate Gaussian network. The construction defined by

$$q = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1, \quad a_q = q - 1, \tag{48}$$

where $d = \gcd(a, b)$, constructs two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles in G_α . It applies uniformly to $d = 1, d > 1$, odd d , and even d .

Proof. If $d = 1$, no switch is used. The horizontal edges form one Hamiltonian cycle and the vertical edges form a second Hamiltonian cycle, as in the known coprime case [2]. These cycles are edge-disjoint because they use different dimensions.

Now, assume $d > 1$. Lemma 2 shows that H_1 is Hamiltonian. Lemma 4 shows that H_2 is Hamiltonian. Lemma 5 shows that their edge sets are disjoint and partition the edge set of G_α :

$$E(H_1) \cap E(H_2) = \emptyset, \quad E(H_1) \cup E(H_2) = E(G_\alpha). \tag{49}$$

Thus, H_1 and H_2 are two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles. The proof does not depend on whether d is odd or even. □

Corollary 1. For $d > 1$, the two cycles have the following edge-type counts:

$$|E(H_1) \cap E_h| = N - 2(d - 1), \tag{50}$$

$$|E(H_1) \cap E_v| = 2(d - 1), \tag{51}$$

$$|E(H_2) \cap E_h| = 2(d - 1), \tag{52}$$

$$|E(H_2) \cap E_v| = N - 2(d - 1). \tag{53}$$

Proof. Each of the $d - 1$ switches removes two horizontal edges from H_1 and inserts two vertical edges into H_1 . Thus, H_1 contains $N - 2(d - 1)$ horizontal edges and $2(d - 1)$ vertical edges. Since H_2 is the complement, it contains the opposite counts. □

6. Algorithms

This section gives explicit algorithms for constructing the two Hamiltonian cycles. Algorithm 1 constructs the switch sets. Algorithm 2 determines cycle membership for any vertex in constant time. Algorithm 3 lists the Hamiltonian-cycle order.

Algorithm 1: ConstructSwitchSets(a, b)**Require:** Generator $\alpha = a + bi, 0 < a \leq b$ **Ensure:** Removed set R and inserted set S

```

1:  $d \leftarrow \gcd(a, b); N \leftarrow a^2 + b^2; r \leftarrow N/d$ 
2: Find  $u, v$  such that  $ua + vb = d$ 
3:  $n \leftarrow av - bu \pmod{r}$ 
4:  $R \leftarrow \emptyset, S \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5: for  $q = 1$  to  $d - 1$  do
6:    $a_q \leftarrow q - 1$ 
7:    $A \leftarrow (a_q, q); B \leftarrow (a_q + 1, q)$ 
8:    $C \leftarrow A + i$  using the rectangle move
9:    $D \leftarrow B + i$  using the rectangle move
10:   $R \leftarrow R \cup \{AB, CD\}$ 
11:   $S \leftarrow S \cup \{AC, BD\}$ 
12: end for
13: return  $R, S$ 

```

Algorithm 2: CycleNeighbors(v, R, S)**Require:** Vertex v , switch sets R, S **Ensure:** The two neighbors of v in H_1 and in H_2

```

1:  $N_G(v) \leftarrow \{v \pm 1, v \pm i\}$ 
2:  $N_1 \leftarrow \emptyset; N_2 \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: for each  $w \in N_G(v)$  do
4:    $e \leftarrow \{v, w\}$ 
5:   if  $e \in S$  or ( $e$  is horizontal and  $e \notin R$ ) then
6:      $N_1 \leftarrow N_1 \cup \{w\}$ 
7:   else
8:      $N_2 \leftarrow N_2 \cup \{w\}$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: return  $N_1, N_2$ 

```

Algorithm 3: TraverseCycle(s, N_C)**Require:** Start vertex s , neighbor function $N_C(\cdot)$ for H_1 or H_2 **Ensure:** Vertex order of the Hamiltonian cycle

```

1:  $L \leftarrow [s]; \text{prev} \leftarrow \perp; \text{cur} \leftarrow s$ 
2: repeat
3:   Let  $N_C(\text{cur}) = \{z_1, z_2\}$ 
4:   if  $z_1 \neq \text{prev}$  then
5:      $\text{next} \leftarrow z_1$ 
6:   else
7:      $\text{next} \leftarrow z_2$ 
8:   end if
9:    $\text{prev} \leftarrow \text{cur}; \text{cur} \leftarrow \text{next}$ 
10:  if  $\text{cur} \neq s$  then
11:    append  $\text{cur}$  to  $L$ 
12:  end if
13: until  $\text{cur} = s$ 
14: return  $L$ 

```

Complexity

The switch rule computes each switch using a constant number of arithmetic operations. Therefore, constructing the switch sets takes $O(d)$ time. Since each Hamiltonian cycle has N edges, listing either cycle takes $O(N)$ time. The total cycle-generation time is therefore $O(N)$, and the local rule for each switch is constant time.

7. Examples

7.1. Example 1: The Coprime Case $\alpha = 3 + 5i$

Here,

$$d = \gcd(3,5) = 1, \quad N = 34. \tag{54}$$

The switch set is empty. The first Hamiltonian cycle is obtained by repeatedly adding 1, and the second is obtained by repeatedly adding i . Thus, the construction reduces exactly to the previously known $d = 1$ case.

7.2. Example 2: The Non-Coprime Case $\alpha = 4 + 4i$

Here,

$$d = 4, \quad N = 32, \quad r = 8. \tag{55}$$

The switches are

$$(q, a_q) = (1, 0), (2, 1), (3, 2). \tag{56}$$

The first two switches connect consecutive rows without wrap-around:

$$(0, 1)(1, 1), (0, 2)(1, 2), \tag{57}$$

$$(1, 2)(2, 2), (1, 3)(2, 3). \tag{58}$$

The final switch uses the wrap from row 3 to row 0:

$$A_3 = (2, 3), \quad B_3 = (3, 3), \tag{59}$$

and because $n = 4$,

$$C_3 = (6, 0), \quad D_3 = (7, 0). \tag{60}$$

This produces

$$H_1 : 26 \text{ horizontal edges} + 6 \text{ vertical edges}, \tag{61}$$

and

$$H_2 : 6 \text{ horizontal edges} + 26 \text{ vertical edges}. \tag{62}$$

The switch data for this example are

q	a_q	A_q, B_q	C_q, D_q
1	0	$(0, 1), (1, 1)$	$(0, 2), (1, 2)$
2	1	$(1, 2), (2, 2)$	$(1, 3), (2, 3)$
3	2	$(2, 3), (3, 3)$	$(6, 0), (7, 0)$.

(63)

The last switch is the wrap switch from row 3 to row 0.

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the complete construction for G_{4+4i} . Figure 3 shows the two Hamiltonian cycles separately: H_1 uses the switched horizontal structure, while H_2 uses the complementary vertical structure. Figure 4 draws the two cycles together, with H_1 in blue and H_2 in red. The combined drawing emphasizes edge-disjointness: any crossings are geometric crossings in the drawing only and are not shared graph edges.

Figure 3. The two Hamiltonian cycles for G_{4+4i} shown separately. (a) The cycle H_1 is obtained from the horizontal row-cycle structure by applying the switch operations; the red edges are the inserted vertical switch edges. (b) The cycle H_2 is obtained from the complementary vertical structure; the red edges are the horizontal switch edges removed from H_1 and assigned to H_2 .

Figure 4. Combined drawing of the two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles in G_{4+4i} . The cycle H_1 is drawn in blue and the cycle H_2 is drawn in red. The two cycles have no common graph edge, i.e., $E(H_1) \cap E(H_2) = \emptyset$. Crossings in the drawing are visual crossings only and do not represent shared edges.

7.3. Example 3: An Odd Non-Coprime Case $\alpha = 5 + 10i$

For $\alpha = 5 + 10i$,

$$d = 5, \quad N = 125, \quad r = 25. \tag{64}$$

The switch sequence is

$$(q, a_q) = (1, 0), (2, 1), (3, 2), (4, 3). \tag{65}$$

The validation gives

$$|H_1| = |H_2| = 125, \tag{66}$$

and the edge decomposition is

$$H_1 : 117 \text{ horizontal} + 8 \text{ vertical}, \tag{67}$$

$$H_2 : 8 \text{ horizontal} + 117 \text{ vertical}. \tag{68}$$

8. Experimental Validation

The mathematical proof establishes the correctness of the construction. The purpose of the computational validation is different: it confirms that the closed-form rule is implemented correctly and demonstrates that explicit cycle generation scales in practice. A Python 3.14 validation program was written to test the construction. For each generator $\alpha = a + bi$, the program computes d, r, n , constructs the switch sets, verifies the degree of every vertex in H_1 and H_2 , traverses each cycle, and confirms that each traversal visits all N vertices exactly once. It also records edge-type counts and runtime. The degenerate network $\alpha = 1 + i$ with $N = 2$ is excluded because the four formal directions collapse to a single undirected edge.

The validator checks four correctness conditions for every nondegenerate input. First, every vertex has degree two in H_1 and degree two in H_2 . Second, a traversal of H_1 returns one cycle containing all N vertices, and the same condition is checked independently for H_2 . Third, the edge sets are tested for disjointness, i.e., $E(H_1) \cap E(H_2) = \emptyset$. Finally, the measured horizontal and vertical edge counts are compared with the closed-form counts in Corollary 1.

8.1. Validation Scope

The validation included:

- 18 representative cases covering $d = 1, d > 1$, odd d , even d , small networks, and large networks;
- exhaustive validation for all $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$;
- large-scale validation up to $N = 3,250,000$ (see Tables 2–4).

Table 2. Representative validation of the closed-form EDHC construction.

α	d	r	N	$ H_1 $	$ H_2 $	Result
$3 + 5i$	1	34	34	34	34	Yes
$4 + 4i$	4	8	32	32	32	Yes
$3 + 6i$	3	15	45	45	45	Yes
$5 + 10i$	5	25	125	125	125	Yes
$6 + 6i$	6	12	72	72	72	Yes
$6 + 8i$	2	50	100	100	100	Yes
$8 + 8i$	8	16	128	128	128	Yes
$8 + 12i$	4	52	208	208	208	Yes
$10 + 15i$	5	65	325	325	325	Yes
$12 + 12i$	12	24	288	288	288	Yes
$15 + 20i$	5	125	625	625	625	Yes
$20 + 30i$	10	130	1300	1300	1300	Yes
$25 + 35i$	5	370	1850	1850	1850	Yes
$50 + 50i$	50	100	5000	5000	5000	Yes
$60 + 80i$	20	500	10,000	10,000	10,000	Yes
$100 + 100i$	100	200	20,000	20,000	20,000	Yes
$100 + 150i$	50	650	32,500	32,500	32,500	Yes
$200 + 300i$	100	1300	130,000	130,000	130,000	Yes

Table 3. Edge-type decomposition of the two Hamiltonian cycles.

α	d	H_1^h	H_1^v	H_2^h	H_2^v	$2(d - 1)$
$3 + 5i$	1	34	0	0	34	0
$4 + 4i$	4	26	6	6	26	6
$3 + 6i$	3	41	4	4	41	4
$5 + 10i$	5	117	8	8	117	8
$6 + 6i$	6	62	10	10	62	10
$6 + 8i$	2	98	2	2	98	2
$8 + 8i$	8	114	14	14	114	14
$8 + 12i$	4	202	6	6	202	6
$10 + 15i$	5	317	8	8	317	8
$12 + 12i$	12	266	22	22	266	22
$20 + 30i$	10	1282	18	18	1282	18
$50 + 50i$	50	4902	98	98	4902	98
$100 + 100i$	100	19,802	198	198	19,802	198
$200 + 300i$	100	129,802	198	198	129,802	198

Table 4. Aggregate correctness summary.

Category	Cases	Checked	Successes	Failures
All	5076	5075	5075	0
Exhaustive $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$	5050	5049	5049	0
Large scale	8	8	8	0
Representative	18	18	18	0
$d = 1$	3045	3044	3044	0
$d > 1$	2031	2031	2031	0
Odd d	3781	3780	3780	0
Even d	1295	1295	1295	0

Note: The single case $\alpha = 1 + i$ with $N = 2$ is excluded as degenerate because the four formal directions collapse to one undirected edge. Therefore, rows that include this case have Checked = Cases - 1. The exclusion is not a validation failure.

8.2. Interpretation of the Experiments

The exhaustive test contains 5050 generator pairs with $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$. The only excluded pair is $\alpha = 1 + i$, where $N = 2$. Therefore, 5049 nondegenerate exhaustive cases were checked and all passed. The validation also separately confirms the important categories $d = 1$, $d > 1$, odd d , and even d . The large-scale tests show linear behavior, because the validation time grows approximately proportionally with N (see Table 5).

Table 5. Runtime scalability of the validation procedure.

α	d	N	Total ms	$\mu\text{s}/\text{Node}$
$100 + 100i$	100	20,000	521.907	26.095350
$100 + 150i$	50	32,500	892.941	27.475108
$200 + 200i$	200	80,000	2223.681	27.796012
$200 + 300i$	100	130,000	5310.403	40.849254
$500 + 500i$	500	500,000	16,605.924	33.211848
$500 + 750i$	250	812,500	26,680.321	32.837318
$1000 + 1000i$	1000	2,000,000	68,336.990	34.168495
$1000 + 1500i$	500	3,250,000	112,296.254	34.552694

9. Discussion

The construction has two complementary interpretations. First, it is a unifying theorem: the same rule covers both the old coprime case and the non-coprime case. Second, it is

an algorithmic proof: the switches are not found by search and are not described by long tables. They are given by one formula.

The key design choice is to omit the row adjacency $0 \leftrightarrow 1$ from the horizontal-cycle splicing and instead include the wrap adjacency $(d-1) \leftrightarrow 0$. This makes H_1 join rows through

$$0 - (d-1) - (d-2) - \dots - 1, \quad (69)$$

while the complement H_2 joins vertical cycle indices through

$$0 - 1 - 2 - \dots - (d-1). \quad (70)$$

Thus, one set of switches creates two different spanning splice trees: one for the horizontal cycles and one for the vertical cycles.

A practical advantage of the closed-form rule is that it is local and coordinate based. A node with rectangle coordinate (x, y) can determine whether one of its incident edges is part of a switch by checking a simple coordinate condition for the relevant row adjacency. This is more scalable than a lookup-table-based construction and suggests a distributed implementation in which nodes compute their cycle membership from local coordinates.

The construction also has direct application prospects in interconnection networks. The two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles provide two independent spanning rings that can be used for broadcast scheduling, all-to-all circulation, load-balanced communication, or backup routing after edge failures. The feasibility of such uses follows from the small amount of state needed to generate the cycles: the global parameters d , r , and n , together with the local coordinate (x, y) , determine whether an edge belongs to H_1 or H_2 . Thus, the method can support lightweight route generation without storing long parity-dependent tables at the nodes.

10. Future Directions

The present construction uses the minimal two-edge splicing operation: two edges are removed and two valid replacement edges are inserted. This choice is natural because Hamiltonian cycles are 2-regular, and the operation preserves degree two while each individual operation joins exactly two cycles into one. A possible extension is to study multi-switch operations that remove more than two edges and insert a larger set of replacement edges. Such operations would require additional conditions to preserve degree two at every vertex, maintain connectedness, and keep the resulting Hamiltonian cycles edge-disjoint.

Another direction is to construct EDHCs subject to additional constraints, such as avoiding prescribed faulty edges, minimizing the number of wrap-around switch edges, balancing traffic over geometric regions, or forcing certain vertices or links to appear in a specified cycle. These constrained variants are not addressed by the present theorem, but the coordinate form of the rule provides a useful starting point for them.

A third direction is to extend the algorithmic viewpoint to more general families of algebraic or hypercube-like networks. The present rule relies on the rectangular representation of Gaussian networks and on the arithmetic relation between n , d , and r . Other network families may require different local splice rules, but the same proof strategy (identify cycle decompositions, choose a sparse splice tree, and verify edge-disjoint complementary cycles) may be useful in broader EDHC constructions.

11. Conclusions

This paper presented a unified constant-time switch rule for constructing two edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles in Gaussian networks. The unification has three parts: it covers both $d = 1$ and $d > 1$, it treats odd and even values of d with the same formula, and it

replaces two parity-dependent sequence tables by the single rule $a_q = q - 1$. The rule is simply to switch row adjacency q at column $a_q = q - 1$ for $q = 1, \dots, d - 1$. The switched horizontal graph is one Hamiltonian cycle, and its edge-complement is the second Hamiltonian cycle; the two cycles are edge-disjoint by construction.

The construction is compact, readily implementable, and runs in linear time for explicit cycle generation. Exhaustive and large-scale validation confirmed the result for all tested nondegenerate Gaussian networks, including all generators with $1 \leq a \leq b \leq 100$ and large networks up to 3,250,000 vertices. Because the rule is coordinate-based, it is also suitable for practical settings in which spanning rings must be generated locally for broadcast, all-to-all communication, or fault-tolerant routing without storing large lookup tables.

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